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ABSTRACT

Several global policy forums, agencies, and international organizations actively seek to take immediate action to guarantee and improve the provision of multiple soil-based ecosystem services (SESs). Global changes, such as climate change and land use, potentially contribute to modifying the level of SESs. In addition, SESs interact and should thus be analyzed jointly for a thorough understanding of their synergies and co-occurrences. The identification and analysis of such coherent associations, often referred to as "bundles", is an integrated means of assessing and visualizing these interactions.

This report presents the spatial assessment of soil-based ecosystem services bundles for current period 1980 (called current period hereafter) and projections to 2050, under land use change and two climate change scenarios corresponding to two contrasted Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5). The SESs evaluated at the European Union (EU) scale in this SERENA deliverable were selected through a prioritization assessment made by SERENA partners. The SESs considered as the most important were primary biomass production, climate regulation, soil erosion control, and hydrological control. The last SES includes two sub-services, water production and flood control. Indicators used to assess these SESs were selected based on scientific soundness, data availability, and stakeholder relevance. As a result, net primary production (NPP) is used as an indicator for primary biomass production; net ecosystem productivity (NEP) as indicator for climate regulation; amount of soil not eroded by water as indicator of soil erosion control; water yield for water production; soil water retention capacity as indicator for flood control. All the evaluations were carried out for the current period and projected for 2050 based on available European spatial databases, i.e. SoilGrids for soil data, WorldClim for climate covariates, and LUISA for land use scenarios. To assess primary biomass production, the net primary production produced by the UKESM1 0 LL Dynamic Global Vegetation Models was used for both periods. The same approach was used for climate regulation. Soil erosion control was quantified through the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) for the two periods. We assessed it considering the actual land use and bare soil, and then we calculated the difference between the two soil erosion assessments. Water production was assessed through the difference between precipitation and evapotranspiration potential for the two periods. To assess flood control, soil water retention capacity was calculated based soil water content at field capacity provided by SoilGrids for the present situation and projected in the future using a digital soil mapping approach through Quantile Regression Forest algorithm. Before computing bundles, we classified the evaluations into 3 classes based on the SES values corresponding to the 40th and 60th sample quantiles of the considered SES at the EU scale for the current period. We finally applied a scoring approach to identify bundles of SESs allowing us to map and explore the complex pattern of spatially interacting processes.

Twenty-two bundles for the three scenarios were identified and interpreted in terms of SESs level. Around 1% of the soil in the EU in the current period is represented by the group of bundles that contain a low level of five SESs, located mostly in the southern EU. This group decreased by 2050 under SSP1-2.6. Another 8.7% of soils exhibits low to moderate level of SESs. 23.5% of the EU in the current period is represented by the group of bundles comprising soils that provide a high level of only one SES. Around 32% of soils in the EU in the current period are represented by the group of bundles that contain a high level of two SESs, which increased by almost 10% for both scenarios in 2050. 26.5% of the EU in the current period is represented by the group of bundles comprising soils that provide a high level of three SESs, which decreased by almost 3% in some bundles of this group for SSP5-8.5 scenario in 2050. Around 7% of the soils in the EU in the current period are represented by the group of bundles that contain a high level of four SESs, which, in 2050, doubled in size in both scenarios. At last, around 1% of soils in the EU in the current period are represented by the group of bundles that contain a high level of five SESs. By 2050, this bundle will increase by 2% for both scenarios.

Further steps will consist in (1) a quantitative analysis of the relationships between the spatial distribution of SES bundles and that of the potential bundle drivers such as climate zones, land use and soil types; (2) gathering the feedback from stakeholders on the final output of the work at European scale.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AOA	Area of Applicability
BiomProd	Primary Biomass Production
ClimReg	Greenhouse Gases and Climate Regulation
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CV	Coefficient of Variation
DSM	Digital Soil Mapping
EEA	European Environment Agency
ErosCont	Soil Erosion Control
ESDAC	European Soil Data Centre
ETP	Evapotranspiration Potential
EU	European Union
FAMD	Factorial Analysis for Mixed Data
FloodCont	Flood Control
GCM	Global Coupled Model
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPP	Gross Primary Productivity
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISIMIP	Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project
LUISA	Land Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
MCA	Multivariate Correspondence Analysis
NEP	Net Ecosystem Productivity
NPP	Net Primary Productivity
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OOB	Out-Of-Bag
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PI	Prediction Interval
PTF	Pedotransfer Function
QRF	Quantile Regression Forest
R ²	Coefficient of Determination
RF	Random Forest
RFE	Recursive Feature Elimination
RH	Heterotrophic Respiration
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
SD	Standard Deviation
SES	Soil Ecosystem Service
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
SSP	Shared Socio-economic Pathways
SWRC	Soil Water Retention Capacity
WatProd	Water Production

WoSIS World Soil Information Service
WP Work Package

1. Introduction

In recent years, the European Union (EU) has drawn attention to the importance of the evaluation of multiple soil-based ecosystem services (SESs) and the use of such evaluations in the implementation of different sustainability policies (Schulte et al., 2015; Stavi and Lal, 2015). The recent ongoing work on the new EU directive on soil monitoring and resilience (also called “soil monitoring law”) aims to ensure that soils are managed sustainably and that their capacity to provide ecosystem services is maintained (European Commission, 2023). This directive aligns with many other EU strategies, such as the European Green Deal and the EU Soil Strategy for 2030, which provide targets to achieve healthy soils by 2050, to continue providing essential ecosystem services (European Commission, 2019; 2020). Moreover, one of the new challenges for SES evaluation is to provide research on the multiple interactions of the SESs.

The SESs to be evaluated at the European scale in this SERENA deliverable were selected through a prioritization assessment of the most important SESs by each SERENA Member State (MS) partner considering end-user's requirements and EU expectations (Reyes-Rojas et al., in prep.). The most important SESs identified are primary biomass production, climate regulation, soil erosion control, and hydrological control. There are several definitions for SESs in the literature that were critically analyzed in the SERENA project to adopt the most coherent one (Antón et al., 2022) and asked the stakeholder's opinion on them. For the considered SESs, the consolidated and validated definitions are:

Primary biomass production: *capacity of a soil to supply humans with food, feed, fiber, fuel, wood, pharmaceuticals and biochemistry.*

Climate regulation: *capacity of soil to reduce the amount of GHG emissions in the atmosphere.*

Soil erosion control: *reduction in the loss of soil material by virtue of the stabilizing effects of the presence of plants and animals that mitigate or prevent potential damage to human use of the environment or human health and safety.*

Hydrological control: *capacity of a soil to receive, store, conduct and supply water for subsequent use while minimizing the effects of prolonged droughts, flooding and erosion.* Two aspects of hydrological control were separately considered in our analysis - **Water production** and **Flood control**.

SESs do not occur independently, but co-occur, interacting and potentially influencing each other, this coexistence is called "bundles" (Mouchet et al., 2017). SES bundles are defined by Raudsepp-Hearne et al. (2010) as a set of soil-based ecosystem services that appear together repeatedly in space and time. This definition was adopted in SERENA. There is a growing body of knowledge available on SES interactions at the country and regional scales (Jopke et al., 2015; Maes et al., 2012; Mouchet et al., 2017; Orsi et al., 2020; Plieninger et al., 2019; Ungaro et al., 2022), but the complexity and interaction of multiple SESs at continental scale still needs to be explored. To address this concern, the SERENA project aims to provide relevant information for soil policy by assessing and identifying SES-bundles across the EU.

Several methodologies exist in the literature to evaluate SES bundles. Saidi and Spray (2018) distinguished two main strategies that accounted for more than 90% of the studies: cluster analyses (k-means or hierarchical) and graphical/tabular detection using lower dimensional projections with principal component analysis (PCA) (Maes et al., 2012; Mouchet et al., 2014; Raudsepp-Hearne et al., 2010), factor analysis (Mouchet et al., 2014), multiple correspondence analysis (MCA), or multidimensional scaling (Richards et al., 2020), or the most recent study by Právělie et al. (2024), using a scoring approach.

Finally, global change (that is climate and land use change), will have an impact on the provision of the SESs, directly influencing its delivery (Mouchet et al., 2017; Saidi and Spray, 2018). Global temperatures are expected to rise by 1 to 2°C by 2050, which will change precipitation patterns (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2023). This climate change threatens food security by affecting soil processes (Brevik, 2013). Along with climate change, population growth and the increasing need for biomass for energy will lead to changes in land use. These changes will impact on the services provided by soils, but our understanding of such changes on SESs is just starting to be developed.

The identification of SES-bundles at EU scale under current socio-environmental conditions, and the assessment of their evolution under the influence of climate and land use changes by 2050, are important for well-informed decision-making by the EU within the framework of its soil policy to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal (EC-European Commission, 2019). Therefore, the objective of this report is to present the spatial assessment of SES-bundles for what has been considered present (1960-2019) and for 2050, considering the effects of land use and climate changes at the EU scale. To achieve this, we developed a top-down mapping approach based on the European datasets.

Considering the global change scenarios, we chose two of the climatic projections produced by the five emissions scenarios defined by the IPCC, the so-called Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). We consider only the two extreme SSPs: SSP1-2.6, envisioning a sustainable, low-emission pathway with stringent mitigation measures, and SSP5-8.5, representing a high-emission scenario driven by continued fossil fuel use and limited mitigation efforts with severe impacts on climate (Eyring et al., 2016; O'Neill et al., 2017; Riahi et al., 2017). We also considered the land use change projected for 2050 by the Land Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment (LUIA) model (Joint Research Centre, 2015).

The report is divided into two parts: the assessment of the spatial distribution of the five selected individual SESs and the detection and mapping of the SES-bundles for both the current period and by 2050. Figure 1.

2. Assessment of soil ecosystem services: Conceptual reflexion and indicators

2.1. Material and methods

In this section, we first discuss the indicators chosen for the different SESs, then the methods used to assess them followed by the sources of data used and finally the way the data is presented.

2.1.1. Soil-based ecosystem service definitions and indicators choice

SESs are assessed by indicators. However, for a given SES, numerous indicators exist in the literature (Reyes-Rojas et al., in prep.). SERENA task 2.3 evaluated, *for each SES*, the scientific soundness of these indicators based on various criteria and defined “ideal” indicators (those with a higher level of scientific soundness to fit the SESs in question) and “pragmatic” indicators (those which are generally used in currently available information) (D2.3.1 in section 4.2; Montagne et al., 2023). Based on their analysis, for each of the considered SESs, we selected the indicators to be assessed at the European scale; they correspond to what is considered as “pragmatic” indicators (Table 1).

Table 1. Indicators chosen to assess soil-based ecosystem services at the European scale (based on SERENA T2.3)

Soil-based ecosystem services	Indicator	Short definition
Primary biomass production	Net primary production (gC m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)	Carbon gained by plants through photosynthesis minus respiration losses.
Soil erosion control	Amount of soil not eroded by water (t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Total amount of soil that has not been eroded by water due to the protective effect of natural or cultivated vegetation
Climate regulation	Net ecosystem productivity (gC m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)	Net primary productivity minus heterotrophic respiration
Water production	Water yield (mm yr ⁻¹)	Amount of rainfall water that does not evapotranspire
Flood control	Soil water retention capacity (mm)	Amount of water storable in the whole soil profile

It should be noted that:

- (1) in the case of soil erosion control, the choice of a pragmatic indicator modifies the definition of this SES, limiting it to the sole water erosion control and neglecting the control of soil erosion by wind, tillage and harvest.
- (2) among these SESs, the indicators chosen for BiomProd, ClimReg and WatProd, are not directly or not at all related to soil properties.

2.1.2. Soil-based ecosystem services indicators' spatial assessment and projection

Figure 1 summarizes the approaches chosen to spatially evaluate the individual SESs at the European scale. We decided to perform the evaluation of the individual SESs at a resolution of 1 km cell size using available maps or, if maps were not available, by producing our own maps.

Figure 1. Overall modelling framework for mapping the SES bundles for the current situation and by 2050 based on a comprehensive assessment of five soil ecosystem services

2.1.2.1. Assessment by soil water retention capacity over one-meter depth of flood control

2.1.2.1.1. DSM estimation of the soil water retention capacity under current condition

To assess flood control under current conditions and projected scenarios for 2050, estimations of soil water retention capacity (SWRC) over the whole soil depth or over one-meter depth for deeper soils at two different dates are needed. For the current situation, SWRC was calculated based equation 1 based on data of soil water content at saturation θ_{FC}^h available in SoilGrids (Turek et al., 2023, based on soil profiles collected by ISRIC's World Soil Information Service (WoSIS), Batjes et al., 2019) and soil depth t_h available ESDAC center from the European map at 1:1 million scale. For WoSIS, the soil profiles were sampled mainly between 1960 and 2019 with a median sampling date of 1980 that will thus be considered as the date of the current situation.

We compute SWRC over the whole soil depth or over one meter for soils deeper than 1-meter, using the following equation:

$$SWRC = \sum_{h=1}^n \theta_{FC}^h t_h \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number of layers of SoilGrids (6) and t_h is the effective thickness of the horizon in mm (that can be truncated for the deepest layer depending on soil profile thickness estimates).

To project SWRC to 2050, we applied a space-for-time substitution approach (Lugato et al., 2021) under a DSM framework (Grunwald et al., 2011; McBratney et al., 2003; Minasny and McBratney, 2016). DSM is a modern way of creating soil maps and spatial soil information systems using numerical models. DSM relies on empirical quantitative descriptions of relationships between soil and environmental factors with a view to using these as soil spatial prediction functions. In our work, a model based on the Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) algorithm was trained on the current

environmental factors as a first step. In a second step, the covariates supposed to evolve from the current period to the 2050 conditions (climate, land use and SOC content) were replaced in the model for the 2050 spatial predictions, after verifying that we are not going out of application range of the model.

To compute SOC content, as over a time range of 70 years (1980 -2050), only a part of the SOC is likely to evolve. We therefore assessed the SOC content for 2050 by applying a DSM to the only SOC part likely to evolve. This part was estimated applying the proportion of SOC younger than 70 years estimated by Balesdent et al. (2018) for the different soil depths. Final (2050) SOC content was then calculated adding the fraction of SOC likely to evolve over 70 years estimated by DSM, to the fraction of SOC not likely to evolve, estimated for each soil on the 1980's data.

To optimize DSM model for the current period, prior to modeling, only key covariates that are not strongly correlated were selected (Spearman correlation coefficient lower than 0.9). Then, Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) was employed to select the most important covariates (Xu et al., 2019). Removing unnecessary features can reduce the computational expense and time consumption, thus generating more robust models. We used the RFE algorithm implemented in the *caret* package (Kuhn, 2008) in the R software (R Core Team, 2020). RFE starts by fitting the model using all covariates, evaluating its performance and ranking the importance, then the less important covariates are removed. The selection of the best covariate subset was based on out-of-bag (OOB) cross-validation with 15-folds and two repetitions and accuracy metrics, such as R^2 and RMSE. For land use, as the chosen resolution to map the SES (1 km cell size) is coarser than the initial land use data resolution (100 m cell size), the proportion of each land use class in the 1 km cell size was used.

QRF is an extension of RF that provides non-parametric estimates (Meinshausen, 2006; Meinshausen and Schiesser, 2015), and it was implemented by using the R package *ranger* (Wright and Ziegler, 2017). For each time, the median values were computed to characterize the distribution of SWRC. To calibrate the prediction model, we extracted values of SWRC and covariates on a systematic sampling grid of 40,000 pixels.

The model was tuned by a 15-folds cross-validation and two repetition procedure, applied to multiple combinations of hyper-parameters (*nmtree* and *mtry*). Cross-validation is an iterative process where the dataset is divided into 15 disjunctive folds. Each fold acts as a validation set in turns to evaluate the predictions obtained from a model calibrated on the remaining 14-folds. This helps to comprehensively evaluate the model's performance on different subsets of the data. To enhance the reliability of the cross-validation process, the 15-folds cross-validation procedure was repeated two times. Each repetition represents an independent run of the 15-folds cross-validation. For each repetition, the dataset is randomly shuffled, and the 15-folds are created again. The metrics of the two replications were averaged. The *nmtree* number was finally set at 200, as already reported by Poggio et al. (2021), since a number above 200 only provides an increase in metrics lower than 0.1% but requires more memory and computation time. Within the different *mtry* numbers tested, *mtry* values were set to half of the total number of covariates.

Therefore, we computed the mean of the different continuous covariates per 1 km cell size.

2.1.2.1.2. Evaluation of the DSM projection model for soil water retention capacity for the current period and by 2050

The evaluation of the DSM model for SWRC was done in two steps: the assessment of the model performance to predict the SWRC on the current data by repeated cross-validation and the assessment of the DSM model domain of applicability by 2050.

Two parameters of accuracy were computed during the cross-validation step: the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 being the optimal value, that is, the coefficient of determination explaining the variance of models. The RMSE has the same unit as the analyzed parameter and measures the model's accuracy. The closer the RMSE is to zero, the more accurate the model.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (2)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

where \hat{y} is the predicted value over the test set, \bar{y} is the average of the observed values, y is the observed value, n is the number of samples with i , an integer ranging from 1 to n .

To evaluate the reliability of the model for the SWRC projection by 2050, we determined its domain of applicability for 2050, or the Area of Applicability (AOA), that represents where the model can be confidently applied based on the similarity of the distributions of the environmental properties (2050) in that area to those present in the training data (current data). If the projection to 2050 significantly differs from those seen in the training data, the model's predictions may become less reliable or even inaccurate. The resulting AOA map provides a visual representation of the regions where the model predictions can be considered reliable. For more details on the methodology see Meyer and Pebesma (2021).

2.1.2.2. *Assessment of erosion control by avoided sheet and rill erosion by water estimated by the revised universal soil loss equation*

To assess ErosCont for the current period and to project it for 2050, we estimated the total amount of soil not eroded by water ($t \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). To calculate this indicator, we evaluated the sheet and rill erosion for the period by using the revised universal soil loss equation (RUSLE) (Renard et al., 1997), considering (1) the actual land use and (2) bare soil. In the first assessment, we used for each pixel the value of the C factor corresponding to each observed land use class. In the second assessment, we used the C factor of bare soil for all the pixels. Finally, we calculated the difference between the two assessments, which is considered as the total amount of soil not eroded by water (equation 4):

$$ErosCont = R \times K \times LS \times (C_{bare} - C_{real}) \times P \quad (4)$$

where ErosCont is the annual total amount of soil not eroded by water ($t \text{ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), R is the rainfall erosivity factor ($\text{MJ mm ha}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), K is the soil erodibility factor ($t \text{ ha}^2 \text{ h ha}^{-2} \text{ MJ}^{-1} \text{ mm}^{-1}$), LS is the slope length and steepness factor (dimensionless), C_{bare} is the soil erosion with bare soil C factor for the entire territory, C_{real} is the soil erosion with real C factor (dimensionless), and P is the conservation practices factor (dimensionless). The meaning and the estimation of these different parameters is explained below.

The rainfall erosivity (R factor) represents the effect of the rainfall on soil erosion. As historical series of monthly precipitation are available at the European scale, we estimated the R factor by the equation of Wischmeier and Smith (1978) (equation 5):

$$R = \sum_{m=1}^{12} 1.735 * 10^{(1.5 * \log\left(\frac{P_m^2}{Pa}\right) - 0.08188)} \quad (5)$$

where P_m is the monthly rainfall (mm) of month m , Pa is the total annual rainfall (mm), R is the rainfall erosivity factor ($\text{MJ cm ha}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$).

To assess the R factor for the current period we used precipitation from interpolated measured data, and to project erosion control for 2050 we used the precipitation produced by the UKESM1-0-LL global climate model for the two chosen SSP1.2-6 and SSP5.8-5 climate change scenarios (Fick and Hijmans, 2017).

The soil erodibility (K factor) represents the vulnerability of the soil to detachment and transport induced by raindrops and surface runoff (Lal, 2001). Soil erodibility is a function of the soil organic carbon (SOC) content and of the soil particle size distribution (equation 6 developed by Sharpley and Williams (1990)):

$$K = \left\{ 0.2 + 0.3 \exp \left[-0.0256 \text{Sand} \left(1 - \frac{\text{Silt}}{100} \right) \right] \right\} \\ * \left(\frac{\text{Silt}}{\text{Clay} + \text{Silt}} \right)^{0.3} * \left[1.0 - \frac{0.25 \text{SOC}}{\text{SOC} + \exp(3.72 - 2.95 \text{SOC})} \right], \\ * \left[1.0 - \frac{0.7 \text{SN}}{\text{SN} + \exp(-5.51 + 22.9 \text{SN})} \right] * 0.1317 \quad (6)$$

where Sand, Silt, Clay and SOC are in percent and $\text{SN} = 1 - \text{Sand}/100$. The K factor is expressed in $\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{h ha}^{-1} \text{MJ}^{-1} \text{mm}^{-1}$.

To project the K factor to 2050, the SOC content by 2050 was used. To project SOC content to 2050, we applied the DSM approach based on the QRF algorithm that was built on the current map. Then, the covariates supposed to evolve from the current period to 2050, climate and land use (SSP1.2-6 and SSP5.8-5), were replaced in the model for the 2050 projections. The same steps as the DSM approach used to evaluate FloodCont were used, including only considering the SOC part likely to evolve. Sand, silt and clay contents were considered as constant over time and obtained from SoilGrids.

The cover-management factor (C factor) represents the impact of the different land uses on the soil losses (Panagos et al., 2015b; Renard et al., 1997). It varies from 0.01 to 1 with the 1 representing bare soil and 0.01 a land cover that provides 99% reduction in soil loss. The C factor for the current period and for 2050 was estimated using the LULC product from LUISA (Joint Research Centre, 2015) for present and 2050, and the C factor reference values from Panagos et al. (2015b). The original LULC product has a 100 m cell size resolution, the proportion of each land use, and its associated C factor, within the 1 km cell size was considered. We also considered the contribution of the unsealed artificialized area in the final evaluation. The C factor value for these areas is the average of all other C factors that can contribute to these areas. The different C factors are listed in the Table 2.

Table 2. Mean C factors for the land uses classes based on Panagos et al. (2015b).

Land use	C factor	Land use	C factor
Arable crops	0.2336	Sclerophyllous vegetation	0.05215
Mixed Crop Livestock	0.1646	Natural Grassland	0.0435
Livestock Production	0.0892	Rice Production	0.15
Forests Mature	0.0011	Sparsely vegetated areas	0.2535
Transitional woodland shrub	0.1823	Urban unsealed	0.14
Vineyards	0.3527	Industrial unsealed	0.14
Fruit trees and berry plantations	0.2188	Infrastructure unsealed	0.14
Olive groves	0.2273	Urban green leisure unsealed	0.14
Moors and heathland	0.0521		

To account for the varying contributions of different land use types that could exist in a 1 km pixel, we implemented a weighted soil erosion rate considering the proportion of each land use class within the pixel (equation 7):

$$\text{Weighted soil erosion} = \sum_i (A_i \times p_i) \quad (7)$$

where A_i is the the annual soil loss ($\text{t ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$) (equation 4) for land use class i within a pixel, p_i is the proportion of land occupied by land use class i within the pixel (where $\sum_i p_i = 1$).

Slope length and steepness (LS factor) describes the effect of topography on soil erosion. We used the LS factors provided by Panagos et al. (2015a).

The conservation practices (P factor) represent the agricultural practices that reduce the mean annual rate of soil loss, such as contour farming, strip cropping, terraces and subsurface drainage. The P factor proposed by Panagos et al. (2015c) for Europe was used.

For both LS and P factors, we used the *aggregate* function in the terra package (Hijmans, 2024) to resample from 100 m cell size to 1 km cell size resolution, applying the mean method to preserve important information.

To evaluate our soil erosion control map, we compared it with the proposed by the European Commission (2015), in the work “Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES)”. Indeed, to the best of our knowledge, there is no soil erosion control map based on observational data.

2.1.2.3. Assessment by net primary production of primary biomass production

For BiomProd, the potential NPP produced by Dynamic Global Vegetation Model (DGVM) UKESM1-0-LL (Sellar et al., 2019) in the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP - <https://www.isimip.org/>) was used as an indicator. The potential NPP is provided in raster format with a spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$, that is around 55 km cell size resolution. We resampled these coarse resolution maps to 1 km cell size (30 arc seconds) using nearest neighbor method, to maintain the original data values. For more details about ISIMIP data refer to <https://protocol.isimip.org/> (table 4.1).

2.1.2.4. Assessment by net ecosystem productivity of climate regulation and greenhouse gases

For climate regulation, NEP was used as an indicator. It represents the net carbon balance of an ecosystem and is calculated as the difference between the amount of carbon taken up by plants through photosynthesis (NPP), and the amount of carbon released through heterotrophic respiration (RH). RH is an important component of the global carbon cycle, as it represents a major pathway through which carbon is returned to the atmosphere (He et al., 2022).

$$NEP = NPP - RH \quad (8)$$

A positive NEP indicates that the ecosystem is a net carbon sink, meaning that it is removing more carbon from the atmosphere than it is releasing. In contrast, a negative NEP indicates that the ecosystem is a net source of carbon, meaning that it is releasing more carbon into the atmosphere than it is absorbing (Feng et al., 2023).

As NPP, NEP was produced by Dynamic Global Vegetation Model (DGVM) UKESM1-0-LL (Sellar et al., 2019) in the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP - <https://www.isimip.org/>), in raster format with a spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$. It was also resampled to reach a resolution of 1 km cell size (30 arc seconds), using nearest neighbor method.

2.1.2.5. Assessment by the water yield of water production

For the water production service, the water yield (mm yr^{-1}) was chosen as an indicator, that is, annual $P - ETP$ for the current period and for 2050 (equation 9). ETP was calculated by a temperature-based approach (Capodici, 2008; Thornthwaite, 1948; equation 10):

$$\text{Water yield} = \text{Precipitation} - ETP \quad (9)$$

where Precipitation is the annual precipitation (mm yr^{-1}); ETP is the evapotranspiration potential (mm yr^{-1}).

$$ETP = 1.6 \left(\frac{10T}{I} \right)^a \quad (10)$$

where T ($^\circ\text{C}$) is the mean monthly air temperature; I is the heat index which is constant for a given location and a is an empirically determined exponent, which is given as a function of I by the following relationship:

$$a = 6.75 * 10^{-7} I^3 * 7.71 * 10^{-5} I^2 + 1.79 * 10^{-2} I + 0.49$$

I is computed as a sum of 12 monthly index values i , where i is a function of the monthly normal temperatures using the following formula:

$$i = \left(\frac{T}{5} \right)^{1.514} \quad (11)$$

$$I = \sum_{j=1}^{12} i_j \quad (12)$$

where i_j is the monthly heat index for the month j (which is zero when the mean monthly temperature is 0°C or less).

2.1.3. Data sources

Since several SES indicators need soil parameters (soil water retention capacity and amount of soil not eroded by water), climate data (soil water retention capacity, amount of soil not eroded by water, water yield, NPP and NEP) or land use data (soil water retention capacity and amount of soil not eroded by water), the use of different databases as input data could induce discrepancies that might arise from the diverse sources' inherent variations when building SES-bundles. To avoid this drawback, we chose a unique soil database per data type, i.e. SoilGrids for soil data, WorldClim for climate covariates, UKESM1-0-LL as DGVM models' outputs for NPP and NEP, and LUISA for land use (Figure 1). Data sources used are summarized in Table 3. For SoilGrids products, the DSM procedure relies on profiles data. About 5 % of the profiles were sampled before 1960, 14 % between 1961–1980, 32 % between 1981–2000 and 16 % between 2001–2019; the date of sampling is unknown for 34 % of the shared profiles (Batjes et al., 2020). We therefore consider the current period (1980).

Table 3. Environmental-based covariates used in the assessment of individual soil-based ecosystem services

Parameters	Variables	Unit	Raw resolution	Source	SES
Climate	Monthly precipitation	mm	1 km	worldclim.org/	WatProd; ErosCont
	Annual precipitation	mm yr ⁻¹			
	Minimum temperature	°C	1 km	worldclim.org/	WatProd
	Maximum temperature	°C			
	Annual mean temperature	°C	1 km	worldclim.org/	FloodCont
	Mean diurnal range	°C			
	Isothermality	No unit			
	Temperature seasonality	°C			
	Max temp of warm month	°C			
	Temp annual range	°C			
	Mean temp of wet quarter	°C			
	Mean temp of driest quarter	°C	mm	Fraction	
	Precipitation of driest month	mm			
	Precipitation seasonality	Fraction			
	Precip of warmest quarter	mm			
Precip of coldest quarter	mm				
Soil	Clay	g 100g ⁻¹	250 m	https://data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#	FloodCont; ErosCont
	Sand	g 100g ⁻¹	250 m		
	Silt	g 100g ⁻¹	250 m		
	Coarse fragments	g 100g ⁻¹	250 m		
	SOC content	g kg ⁻¹	250 m		
	Soil depth	m	1 km	esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/european-soil-database-v2-raster-library-1kmx1km	
Topography	Aspect	No unit	25 m	land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ/eu-dem/eu-dem-v1.1/view	FloodCont; ErosCont
	Elevation	m	25 m		
	Slope	%	25 m ²		
Land use	Land use classes	No unit	100 m	joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/luisa_en	FloodCont; ErosCont
Support Practices	Contour farming	No unit	100 m	esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/themes/support-practices-factor	ErosCont
	Stone walls	No unit	100 m		
	Grass margins	No unit	100 m		
Vegetation	NPP	gC m ² yr ⁻¹	55 km	https://data.isimip.org/search/simulation-round/ISIMIP3b/	BiomProd; ClimReg
	RH	gC m ² yr ⁻¹	55 km		

2.1.4. Thresholding the evaluations of soil-based ecosystem services

The last step of the evaluation of SESs was their classification into SESs intensity levels to facilitate the interpretation of the bundles. To the best of our knowledge, there are no threshold values for SES intensity levels established in the literature for the chosen indicators. We have considered the SES values corresponding to the 40% and 60% quantiles of the current situation to define the thresholds for low and high intensity levels of SES, respectively. These threshold values were then used for the two 2050 scenarios.

2.2. Soil-based ecosystem services on EU territory for current period and for 2050

2.2.1. Current flood control by soils and projection for 2050

2.2.1.1. DSM model for FloodCont: importance of variables and validation

The most important covariates used by the QRF model in the construction of the FloodCont model are related to soil properties, mainly soil depth but also sand, SOC, clay and silt in decreasing order of importance. They were followed by climate attributes (temperature - maximum temperature of the warmest month, annual mean temperature, mean temperature of the driest quarter, temperature seasonality, mean temperature of the wettest quarter, isothermality, temperature annual range - and precipitation - annual precipitation, warmest quarter precipitation, coldest quarter precipitation) and elevation, that can be a proxy of climate (Figure 2). Soil depth, climate, SOC and soil texture covariates were expected, as it is well known that the dynamics of SWRC depend on these factors.

Figure 2. Importance of the covariates used in the QRF model for mapping FloodCont for the current period

The cross-validation of the obtained FloodCont to the SoilGrid raster data (Turek et al., 2023) yielded R^2 of 0.98 and RMSE of 10.95 mm (Table 4), that is an excellent performance. The model can reproduce a large part of the variability of the SoilGrids raster data. However, we must keep in mind that the map produced by SoilGrids is also a model and its uncertainty can be high. The R^2 of their model is low (0.44) with a RMSE of 6.5 mm (Turek et al., 2023).

Table 4. Cross-validation performances of the model for FloodCont applying QRF algorithm on SoilGrids predictions

Indicator	Cross-validation	
	R^2	RMSE
SWRC	0.98	10.95

For the 2050 projection, we determined the AOA of the model (Figure 3A and B). For the two SSPs, the model remains in its applicability domain (pixels in green color) for most EU in 2050, except in areas as northeastern Italy and Slovenia, western Austria and southeastern France and great part of the Cyprus territory. We can thus consider the results of FloodCont prediction for 2050 as reliable.

Figure 3. Area of applicability (AOA) analysis for FloodCont in 2050 considering land use and climate change under SSP1-2.6 (a) and SSP5-8.5 (b). Locations outside the AOA in a and b are shown in red.

2.2.1.2. Flood control maps by soil in EU for current period and by 2050

The mean FloodCont in the EU is 269 mm for the current period, with a minimum of 25 mm and a maximum of 449 mm. In 2050, the mean and median FloodCont, did not significantly change in any of the two considered scenarios compared to the current period, however with the minimum values multiplied by 4 and the maximum values slightly decreasing (Table 5 and Figure 4)

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of FloodCont by EU soil for current period and in 2050 under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5). The values of the 40 and 60% quantiles of the current period were reported as they were used to classify this SES

FloodCont (mm)	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Quantile values	
					40%	60%
Current	269	301	25	449	282	311
SSP1-2.6	268	301	106	415		
SSP5-8.5	269	302	106	415		

Figure 4. Density plot of flood control (mm) for current period and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. Vertical dash lines represent the 40% and 60% quantile values for the current situation.

The spatial distribution of FloodCont in EU for the current period evidences a high level in northern Europe, precisely in Sweden, Finland, Denmark and the Baltic countries, as well as in some regions of Germany, Poland, Romania and Bulgaria. The opposite occurs (i.e., low FloodCont level) in France, Spain, Portugal, Italy, Croatia and surrounding countries (Figure 5A). This spatial distribution Figure 5 somewhat changes between the current period and 2050, notably in France where the service increases while it decreases in Poland notably for scenario SSP1 2.6, as well as in the Baltic countries, Finland and part of Sweden mainly for SSP5 8.5 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Flood control, estimated by the soil water retention capacity over the whole soil profile or over 1m when the soil is deeper, across EU: Classes of flood control level, for the current period (A) and for 2050, considering land use change and two climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (B) and SSP5-8.5 (C).

2.2.2. Current water production by soils and projection by 2050

2.2.2.1. Water production by soil in Europe for current period and by 2050

Currently, WatProd has a mean of 150 mm yr^{-1} in the EU and a median of 130 mm yr^{-1} , with a minimum negative of -730 mm yr^{-1} and a maximum of 3070 mm yr^{-1} (Table 6 and Figure 6). Compared with projections for 2050, we can observe a gradual decrease in the mean and median WatProd (mm yr^{-1}), from the current period (150 and 130 mm yr^{-1} respectively) to the worst climate scenario in 2050 (30

and 20 mm yr⁻¹ respectively). The minimum values also decrease while the maximum increases resulting in an increase of the range in 2050 compared with the current period.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics of water production for current period and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. The values of the 40 and 60% quantiles of the current period were reported as they were used to classify this SES

WatProd (mm yr ⁻¹)	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Quantiles	
					40%	60%
Current	150	130	-730	3070	78	170
SSP1-2.6	60	50	-1018	3170		
SSP5-8.5	30	20	-1070	3150		

Figure 6. Density plot of water production (mm yr⁻¹) for current period and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. Vertical dash lines represent the 40% and 60% quantile values for the current situation.

The spatial distribution of WatProd in the EU currently presents a high level throughout the central and northern EU, most of UK (but south-western England), northern Spain and Portugal, most of France (but the Mediterranean coast and the Paris basin). In most eastern and southern countries on the opposite, we observe a low level of WatProd (Figure 7). In 2050 the largest change in level from this SES is foreseen in France (Figure 7), in the Baltic countries, southern Sweden and Germany where the level of WatProd decreases due to climate change (since only temperature and precipitation are considered for this SES calculation). There is no water production map at EU scale to validate our model and, it is to be kept in mind that, it was produced using ETP equation, that is a simplified estimation of

ETP and has a large uncertainty, and for 2050, it used data of climate projection also subject to uncertainties.

Figure 7. Water production estimated by P-ETP, in Europe for current period (A) and for 2050, considering land use change and two climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (B) and SSP5-8.5 (C).

2.2.3. Current soil erosion control and projection by 2050

2.2.3.1. Current soil erosion control in Europe and by 2050

The mean and median ErosCont for all the periods are around 2 and 0.4 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ respectively, considered a very slight control, with a higher maximum non-eroded soil for the SSP1-2.6 scenario compared to both the current period and SSP5-8.5 (Table 7 and Figure 8).

Table 7. Descriptive statistics of soil erosion control for the current period and the projections by 2050 under land use change and two climate scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5). The values of the 40% and 60% quantiles of the current period were reported as they were used to classify this SE

ErosCont (t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Quantiles	
					40%	60%
Current	1.8	0.40	0	293	0.24	0.62
SSP1-2.6	2.0	0.40	0	370		
SSP5-8.5	1.8	0.40	0	312		

Figure 8. Log-scaled density plot of erosion control (t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) for current situation and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. Vertical dash lines represent the 40% and 60% quantile values for the current situation.

The spatial distribution of ErosCont in the EU in the current period (Figure 9A) presents a high level in a considerable part of France - mainly in the southern part of the country -, in the north of Spain and Portugal, in most of Italy, in central EU, northern Romania, most of Greece and Bulgaria and some regions in UK and Sweden. In other countries such as Poland, Finland, part of Germany and the Baltic countries, there is a low level of ErosCont. Considering the projection by 2050, we cannot identify a significant change in ErosCont affected by climate and land use changes (Figure 9A, B, C).

Figure 9. Soil erosion control is estimated as the quantity of soil not eroded by water (simulated by RUSLE equation) in EU for current period (A) and for 2050, considering land use change and two climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (B) and SSP5-8.5 (C).

2.2.3.2. Comparison of the current soil erosion control map with existing map

We compared the map obtained for the current condition (SERENA) with the one proposed by the European Commission in the work “Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services” (MAES - European Commission, 2015) that also used the RUSLE model but with different values for some of the factors.

The mean value of ErosCont by vegetation proposed for EU by the two approaches strongly differ with 1.8 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for SERENA and 8.4 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for MAES (Table 8) due to strong difference in maximal

values, while the median values are comparable. For comparison purposes, we calculated the proportion of the different ErosCont classes for the two maps. We obtained larger areas with ErosCont potential in the 1-2 and 2-5 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ classes (slight and moderate ErosCont, respectively) (Table 8) Conversely, MAES gathered 23% more areas with high ErosCont (>10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) in comparison with SERENA.

Table 8. Descriptive statistics of soil erosion control (t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) and the proportion of soil erosion control classes in the EU territory (%) in SERENA and MAES outputs

	ErosCont (t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)				ErosCont proportion (%)				
	Mean	Median	Min	Max	0-1	1-2	2-5	5-10	>10
SERENA	1.8	0.37	0.00	293	16	16	21	14	33
MAES	8.4	0.33	0.00	938	12	6.8	13	12	56

These differences are due, as mentioned above, to different values used for the RUSLE equation factors. While we cannot conclude which model has the highest accuracy in estimating ErosCont, it clearly shows the importance of the factor value estimation on the results. It is however to be noted that the spatial distribution proposed by the two models is somewhat comparable.

2.2.4. Current biomass production and projection by 2050

2.2.4.1. Current biomass production in EU and by 2050

For the current period in the EU there is an average BiomProd of 948 gC m⁻² yr⁻¹ and a median of 975 gC m⁻² yr⁻¹. The values range from 32 to 2362 gC m⁻² yr⁻¹ (Table 9 and Figure 10). In Table 9, a slight increase in BiomProd in 2050 for both climate scenarios is foreseen, with a mean and a median of about 1100 gC m⁻² yr⁻¹.

Table 9. Descriptive statistics of biomass production for current period and projection under land use change and two climate scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. The values of the 40 and 60% quantiles of the current period were reported as they were used

Biomass production (gC m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Quantiles	
					40%	60%
Current	948	975	327	2362	899	1052
SSP1-2.6	1084	1110	44	2593		
SSP5-8.5	1130	1149	36	2625		

Figure 10. Density plot of biomass production ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) for current period and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. Vertical dash lines represent the 40% and 60% quantile values for the current situation.

For the current period (Figure 11A), we can see that we have a high level of BiomProd throughout Countries extending from the UK and France to Poland, but also some regions of Romania, and the southern parts of Lithuania and Sweden. On the opposite, in the Mediterranean Countries but also in the Northern Countries, only a lower level of BiomProd is observed. For 2050, the BiomProd Figure 11 increases in Finland and Sweden notably for SSP5-8.5 (Figure 11C).

Figure 11. Biomass production is estimated by NPP in EU for the current period (A) and for 2050, considering the land use change and two climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (B) and SSP5-8.5 (C).

2.2.4.2. Validation of the current NPP map

For validation, we compared the map of NPP produced by the UKESM-0-LL model, the indicator of BiomProd, for the current condition, with that based on remote sensing at the EU scale proposed by European Environment Agency (EEA - European Environment Agency, 2023) and based on MODIS (vegetation indices – Didan, 2021a, 2021b) and ERA5 (meteorological data - Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2018; Figure 12).

In general, the UKESM-0-LL NPP values are higher than those obtained by remote sensing by the EEA, with a mean around 950 gC m⁻² yr⁻¹ for SERENA and 630 gC m⁻² yr⁻¹ for EEA and with larger range (Table

10). The data used by SERENA (UKESM-0-LL) overestimated the NPP mainly in the north of EU (e.g. Poland, Germany, Finland, Sweden, UK) and France, while the southern part of EU is more comparable to the EEA NPP values (Figure 12). However, when compared to data from FLUXNET measurements (Jung et al., 2011) based on eddy covariance technique to measure the gas exchanges (carbon dioxide and water vapor) and energy between the biosphere and atmosphere (Delwiche et al., 2024), the average GPP varied between 134 and 137 PgC yr⁻¹, depending on driving data, similar to the observed data from FLUXNET (between 120 and 140 PgC yr⁻¹), thus showing a reliable output from UKESM (Jung et al., 2011).

Figure 12. Net primary productivity ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) for current period predicted by UKESM-0-LL (and used in SERENA) (A) and estimated by EEA based on remote sensing data (B).

Table 10. Descriptive statistics of net primary productivity ($\text{gC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) for SERENA and EEA outputs

Current period	Mean	Median	Min	Max
SERENA	948	975	32	2362
EEA	627	618	0.0	1962

2.2.5. Current climate regulation in EU and projection by 2050

As already mentioned above, a positive ClimReg value (estimated by NEP) indicates that the ecosystem is a net carbon sink, meaning that it is removing more carbon from the atmosphere than it is releasing. In contrast, a negative ClimReg value indicates that the ecosystem is a net source of carbon, meaning that it is releasing more carbon into the atmosphere than it is absorbing.

For the current period, an average of $29 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ is obtained for the EU territory (Table 11 and Figure 13), with high climate regulation level mainly in the eastern countries and in southern half of France and northern Spain (Figure 14A). In other words, in the EU more carbon is removed from the atmosphere than released. In the SSP1-2.6 scenario, compared to the current period, there is a significant increase in mean and median climate regulation values, suggesting decrease in carbon emissions or an increase in carbon sequestration in this scenario. This increase occurs in all the countries but Sweden, Finland and northern Germany (Figure 14B). Compared to SSP1-2.6, the SSP5-

8.5 scenario shows a decrease in mean and median ClimReg values, reflecting either higher carbon emissions or lower carbon sequestration. The spatial distribution completely changes compared to the current period with high level of climate regulation in southern Spain, Finland, Sweden, UK, Ireland, the Baltic countries and a decrease of this service in part of the eastern countries, France and northern Spain (Figure 14C).

Table 11. Descriptive statistics of climate regulation, estimated by NEP, for current period and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. The values of the 40 and 60% quantiles of the current period were reported as

Climate regulation	Mean	Median	Min	Max	Quantile	
(gC m ⁻² yr ⁻¹)					40%	60%
Current	29	30	-440	325	11	49
SSP1-2.6	88	84	-241	424		
SSP5-8.5	46	47	-464	579		

Figure 13. Density plot of climate regulation (gC m⁻² yr⁻¹) for current period and projection under different climate change scenarios (SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5) by 2050. Vertical dash lines represent the 40% and 60% quantile values for the current situation.

Figure 14. Climate regulation, estimated by NEP, in EU for the current period (A) and for 2050, considering land use change and two climatic scenarios: SSP1-2.6 (B) and SSP5-8.5 (C).

3. Soil-based ecosystem services bundles for the current period and for 2050, assessment and mapping

3.1. Methods of bundle analysis for the different scenarios

As described in section 2.1.2, all the 15 collected spatial databases of the SES assessments were processed at 1 km (5 SESs x 3 scenarios = 15 spatial databases). The SES raw assessments were then transformed into 3 general classes: below the lowest threshold, between the two thresholds and

above the highest threshold (see section 2.1.4), called low, medium and high levels respectively hereafter.

To obtain the bundles for each scenario, the 5 datasets of the scenario were overlaid to indicate the simultaneous presence (co-occurrence) of different classes of SES level, in each pixel. To be able to interpret and investigate the spatial variations of SES bundles, we recoded the 3 SES level classes, scoring them as follows:

- the low SES level was scored to **1**,
- the medium SES level was scored to **10**,
- the high SES level was scored to **100**.

We thus obtained 27 classes considered as bundles and corresponding to the different possible combinations of the 3 possible scores (1, 10 and 100). For example, the score 5 (= 1+1+1+1+1) means a co-occurrence in the pixel of 5 SESs below the low threshold, while 221 (=100+100+10+10+1) means a co-occurrence of 2 SESs higher than the highest threshold (high), 2 SESs in of medium level and 1 SES lower than the lowest threshold (low). This score is a monotone increasing function. It allows comparing the level of co-occurrence of services at the pixel levels but does not allow to identify the services concerned. We applied the same approach for the 3 scenarios using the same thresholds for current scenario and future ones. As the scores are computed in the same way, it possible to compare easily the scenarios.

This approach is adapted from Právělie et al (2024). Medina-Roldán et al. (2024) implemented a similar approach but with scaled values for the SES.

The final SES-bundles map was plotted using the *tmap* R package (Tennekes, 2018).

3.2. Results: Soil-based ecosystem services bundles in the current period and their evolution by 2050 under the effects of land use and climate change scenarios

3.2.1. Current soil-based ecosystem services bundles at the European scale

3.2.1.1. Description of the obtained bundles: number and meaning in terms of SESs

We obtained 21 bundles over the 27 possibilities meaning that some co-occurrences of SES levels do not occur at the EU scale.

We grouped the SES-bundles based on the scoring approach in seven main groups (Figure 15):

- 1- The first group consists of one bundle (score 5), which represent 1.3% of EU (Figure 15) and comprises the soil that provide a low level of service for the five considered SESs.
- 2- The second group is formed by the five bundles comprising soils that provide low to moderate levels of the considered SESs (14, 23, 32, 41 and 50). It represents 8.7% of EU (Figure 15).
- 3- The third group comprises soils that provide a high level of service for one of the considered SESs and is formed by the bundles 104, 113, 122, 131 and 140, which represent 23.5% of EU (Figure 15).
- 4- The fourth group consists of the four bundles comprising soils that provide a high of service for two of the considered SESs (bundle 203, 212, 221 and 230). It represents 32% of EU (Figure 15).
- 5- The fifth group consists of the three bundles comprising soils that provide a high level of service for three of the considered SESs (bundles 302, 311 and 320). It represents 26.5% of EU (Figure 15).

- 6- The sixth group consists of the two bundles comprising soils providing a high level of service for four of the considered SESs (bundles 401 and 410), which represent 7.3% of EU (Figure 15).
- 7- The seventh group consists of the bundle comprising soils that provide a high level of service for the five considered SESs (bundle 500). It represents 0.8% of EU (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Spatial coverage of the European territory by the different SES-bundles for the current period. We considered arbitrarily an uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$ represented by the error bars on the figure. Bundle 5: five SESs at low level; Bundle 14: one SES at moderate and four SESs at low level; 23: two at moderate and three at low level; 32: three at moderate and two at low level; 41: four at moderate and one at low level; 50: five at moderate; 104: one at high and four at low level; 113: one at high, one at moderate and three at low level; 122: one at high, two at moderate and two at low level; 131: one at high, three at moderate and one at low level; 140: one at high and four at moderate level; 203: two at high and three at low level; 212: two at high, one at moderate and two at low level; 221: two at high, two at moderate and one at low level; 230: two at high and three at moderate level; 302: three at high and two at low level; 311: three at high, one at moderate and one at low level; 320: three at high and two at moderate level; 401: four at high and one at low level; 410: four at high and one at moderate level; 500: five SESs at high level.

Figure 16 presents the results of the spatial distribution throughout Europe of the SES bundles. On the one hand, the bundles for soils that provide five SESs at a high level of intensity are located mostly in the central part of France and in the Pyrenees, southern part of Germany and in Northern Ireland and the bundles for soils that provide four SESs in high level are both surrounding the bundle described above and located in southern Sweden, Czechia, Romania and Austria. On the other hand, bundles of soils that provide only low or moderate levels of SESs are located over almost the entire Spanish territory, in southern Portugal, southern and northern France, mainly in the Paris basin, United Kingdom, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and a large area in Finland but not in the eastern countries, and that of soils only with low level for the five SESs in southern EU, mainly in Spain and Italy. At last, the bundles of soils that provide only one high level SES are mainly located in the southern EU, in the Mediterranean areas, but also in Northern France and Germany and in Hungary. As a conclusion, it seems clear that there is a regional distribution of the SES bundles.

Figure 16. Spatial distribution of the SES-bundles in Europe for the current period. Bundle 5: five SESs at low level; Bundle 14: one SES at moderate and four SESs at low level; 23: two at moderate and three at low level; 32: three at moderate and two at low level; 41: four at moderate and one at low level; 50: five at moderate; 104: one at high and four at low level; 113: one at high, one at moderate and three at low level; 122: one at high, two at moderate and two at low level; 131: one at high, three at moderate and one at low level; 140: one at high and four at moderate level; 203: two at high and three at low level; 212: two at high, one at moderate and two at low level; 221: two at high, two at moderate and one at low level; 230: two at high and three at moderate level; 302: three at high and two at low level; 311: three at high, one at moderate and one at low level; 320: three at high and two at moderate level; 401: four at high and one at low level; 410: four at high and one at moderate level; 500: five SESs at high level.

3.2.1.2. Qualitative assessment of the potential drivers of the spatial distribution of the current SES-bundles

To understand the drivers of the regional distribution of the SES-bundles, we visually compared the obtained SES-bundle map with those of potential drivers, such as the current land use, the climate zones and the main soil types (according to the WRB classification) (Figure 17). Some similar spatial features were observed: climate zones and soil types seem to determine the spatial distribution of bundles in Greece (Figure 17A, B, D), while land use seems to explain the spatial distribution in the Baltic Countries (Figure 17A and D) and a combination of land use and climate in northern Spain and Portugal (Figure 18A, B, C), with forested areas corresponding to the high level of ClimReg, WatProd and ErosCont (bundles 212, 302 and 311 on Figure 17A).

This observation is in line with the role of forests in reducing soil erosion, regulating climate and increasing water production, while agricultural areas only poorly contribute to the biomass production, flood control and water production, as discussed by Bozali (2020), Gong et al. (2022) and Vallecillo et al. (2020).

Figure 17. Map of the current SES-bundles for EU (A) and of the potential drivers of the spatial distribution of these bundles: LUISA land use for the current period (B); climate zones of Metzger et al. (2005) (C); dominant soil types according to the WRB classification (D). Acronyms for climate zones are: ALN for alpine north; ALS for alpine south; ATC for Atlantic central; ATN for Atlantic north; BOR for boreal; CON for continental; LUS for Lusitanian; MDM for mediterranean mountains; MDN for mediterranean north; MDS for mediterranean south; NEM for nemoral; PAN for Pannonian.

3.2.2. Projection of soil-based ecosystem service bundles at EU scale by 2050 under land use and climate change scenarios

3.2.2.1. *Spatial distribution of the bundles across Europe in 2050*

The relative abundance and spatial distribution of the SES-bundles significantly differ between the current scenario and the two scenarios for 2050 (Figure 18 and Figure 19). For the bundle with five SESs at low level (bundle 5), there is a decrease in area for SSP1-2.6. For the SSP5-8.5 scenario, there is no change in the total area covered, but in its spatial distribution. In Spain, where this bundle is mainly observed, it is located in the south for the current situation, while it is projected in the north for the SSP5-8.5 scenario (Figure 18 and Figure 19). On the other extreme, SES-bundle with five SESs at high level is projected to increase for both 2050 scenarios, remaining in the same countries for SSP1-2.6 with an increase in the covered area in Germany, France, Ireland, Belgium and the UK, but changing location for SSP5-8.5, from France and Germany where it is projected to disappear, to Austria and Sweden where it is projected to appear, with an increase in UK a(Figure 18 and Figure 19).

SES-bundles with low or moderate level SESs are projected to decrease in coverage area for the two different scenarios for 2050 compared with the current situation, as we can see for example in northern Europe, where this group of bundles decreased significantly, for the SSP5-8.5 scenario. The 203 SES-bundle is projected to increase by almost 10% for both scenarios in 2050 compared to the present situation, as well as the bundle with four high-level SESs (401), which is projected to double in size (Figure 18 and Figure 19).

Figure 18. The respective spatial coverage of the European territory by the different SES-bundles for the current evaluation and the two projected scenarios. We considered arbitrarily an uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$ represented by the error bars on the figure. Bundle 5: five SESs at low level; Bundle 14: one SES at moderate and four SESs at low level; 23: two at moderate and three at low level ; 32: three at moderate and two at low level; 41: four at moderate and one at low level; 50: five at moderate; 104: one at high and four at low level; 113: one at high, one at moderate and three at low level; 122: one at high, two at moderate and two at low level; 131: one at high, three at moderate and one at low level; 140: one at high and four at moderate level; 203: two at high and three at low level; 212: two at high, one at moderate and two at low level; 221: two at high, two at moderate and one at low level; 230: two at high and three at moderate level; 302: three at high and two at low level; 311: three at high, one at moderate and one at low level; 320: three at high and two at moderate level; 401: four at high and one at low level; 410: four at high and one at moderate level; 500: five SESs at high level.

Figure 19. Spatial pattern of the SES-bundles in EU for the current period and by 2050 under land use change and under SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 climate scenarios. Bundle 5: five SESs at low level; Bundle 14: one SES at moderate and four SESs at low level; 23: two at moderate and three at low level; 32: three at moderate and two at low level; 41: four at moderate and one at low level; 50: five at moderate; 104: one at high and four at low level; 113: one at high, one at moderate and three at low level; 122: one at high, two at moderate and two at low level; 131: one at high, three at moderate and one at low level; 140: one at high and four at moderate level; 203: two at high and three at low level; 212: two at high, one at moderate and two at low level; 221: two at high, two at moderate and one at low level; 230: two at high and three at moderate level; 302: three at high and two at low level; 311: three at high, one at moderate and one at low level; 320: three at high and two at moderate level; 401: four at high and one at low level; 410: four at high and one at moderate level; 500: five SESs at high level.

The changes in the spatial distribution of bundles are mainly due to the increase in either biomass production or climate regulation (strongly linked to vegetation growth in the chosen indicators) induced by the temperature increase by 2050. Interestingly the areas that will provide the lower level of services by 2050 do correspond to areas that will be under threats in northern countries but not in southern countries (see the SERENA deliverable D5.1), highlighting no systematic relationship between the level of services provided and the intensity of the soil threats. This rather counterintuitive result may rely on the indicator chosen to assess the different STs and SESs, as Reyes-Rojas et al. (in prep.) clearly demonstrate the influence of this choice on the resulting map.

The further step will thus consist in a quantitative analysis of the relationships among SES bundles and drivers for both the current period and 2050. This will help better interpret the behaviour of SES bundles at the EU scale. Finally, we will gather feedback from stakeholders on the final outputs of our work at both European and national scales to ensure that the bundles maps fit the needs of the European stakeholders.

4. General conclusions

This report presents the assessment at the European scale of individual SESs and SES bundles for the current period and their evolution by 2050 under land use and climate change, considering two contrasting climate scenarios. The considered soil-based ecosystem services are flood control, water production, soil erosion control, biomass production and climate regulation.

Seven main groups of bundles were identified based on the SES levels, ranging from soils providing a high level of the five considered SESs to soils providing a lower level of these five SESs. Around 1% of soils in the EU in the current period are represented by the group of bundles that contain a low level of five SESs, located mostly in the southern EU. Symmetrically, around 1% of soils in the EU in the current period are represented by the group of bundles that contain a high level of five SESs and are located mostly in the central and southern part of France, southern part of Germany and Poland and in Northern Ireland.

Another 8.7% of soils exhibits low to moderate level of SESs, spreading over almost the entire territory of Spain, in southern Portugal, southern and northern France, mainly in the Paris basin, United Kingdom, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and a large area in Finland for the current period. On the opposite, around 7% of soils in the EU in the current period are represented by the group of bundles that contain a high level of four SESs and located mostly in the central and southern part of France, southern part of Germany and Poland, Northern Ireland, southern Sweden, Czechia, Romania and Austria. This symmetrical behaviour may be due to the way the class of level of services were determined in this study showing that the thresholding process is key in interpreting the SES maps and SES bundle maps. More research is needed on that point in the future.

Changes observed in the bundles in future are mainly due to changes in two SESs, climate regulation and biomass production, strongly linked to climate change, while other considered SESs seems poorly sensible to the global change scenarios tested in this study. The impact of global change by 2050, as projected in this study remained relatively limited whatever the scenario considered.

Further steps will consist in (1) a quantitative analysis of the relationships between the spatial distribution of SES bundles and that of the potential bundle drivers such as climate zones, land use and soil types; (2) gathering feedback from stakeholders on the final output of our work both at European and national scales.

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